

UNDERPIN

DATA SPACE FOR MANUFACTURING

Pan-European Data Space for holistic asset management in critical manufacturing industries

D2.2 UNDERPIN Requirements and enablers adaptation final report

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Acronyms and Abbreviations

API	Application Programming Interface
CaaS	Connectors as a Service
CI/CD	Continuous Integration/Continuous Deployment
CLI	Command Line Interface
CRL	Certificate Revocation List
CSRF	Cross-Site Request Forgery
CSVW	CSV on the Web Vocabulary and Syntax Specification
DAPS	Dynamic Attribute Provisioning Service
DAT	Dynamic Attribute Token
DCV	Data Cube Vocabulary
DSSC	Data Spaces Support Centre
EDC	Eclipse Data Space Components
EDC-CE	Eclipse Data Space Connector – Community Edition
EU	European Union
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
HTTPS	Hypertext Transfer Protocol Secure
IAM	Identity and Access Management
IdP	Identity Provider
IDS	International Data Spaces
IDSA	International Data Space Association
IEC	International Electrotechnical Commission
ISMS	Information Security Management System
ISO	International Organization for Standardization
JWT	JSON Web Tokens
K8s	Kubernetes
MS	Member State
MVDS	Minimum Viable Data Space
OAuth2	Open Authorization
OCSP	Online Certificate Status Protocol
OWASP	Open Worldwide Application Security Project
RfP	Request for Proposals
S3	Simple Storage Service
SSO	Single-Sign-On
TLS	Transport Layer Security
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
UC	Use Case
UI	User Interface
URL	Universal Resource Locator
UX	User Experience
W3C	World Wide Web Consortium
WP	Work Package
XSS	Cross-Site Scripting

Executive summary

This Deliverable titled “D2.2 UNDERPIN requirements and enablers adaptation final report” provides the summary of the results of the work carried out in UNDERPIN by month 18 (M18) of the project, with the main focus on the work that has been carried out in Work Package 2 / WP2 (Requirements and Enablers implementation). Furthermore, this deliverable summarises and refers to work results of the work packages: WP3 (Data Space Operational Infrastructure) and WP4 (Use cases for Data Space demonstration and validation), while it also considers the outcomes of the tasks within WP5 (regulatory framework) and WP6 (Standardisation), that are relevant for requirements elicitation and engineering.

The content of this deliverable is thereby:

- a. The final requirements for the UNDERPIN Data Space are presented in Section 2, covering the needs of the Use Cases, the Data Space Components based on the IDS- Reference Architecture Model (RAM) 4.0 and the value-added services.
- b. The overall architecture of the UNDERPIN Data Space, with description of its components, is provided in Section 3.1
- c. A report on the status of the deployment and integration of the UNDERPIN Data Space according to the architecture is provided in Section 3.2

The methodology of requirements elicitation and specification about the UNDERPIN use cases and the UNDERPIN Data Space system (interviews, workshops, desk research) is extensively described in the first iteration of this deliverable, namely D2.1 [1]. Here in D2.2 we provide the final results in detail.

The following 3 main use cases have been identified:

- UC1.1: Monitoring and predictive maintenance in the refinery
- UC2.1: Predictive maintenance in the wind farms
- UC2.2: Wind turbine blade repair prediction

The technical requirements identified and specified show a clear path along the European wide (and beyond) developments of Data Spaces, namely following IDS architecture principles and EDC implementations. The UNDERPIN Data Space is built upon the Eclipse Data Space Components (EDC) and makes use of the Sovity production-ready components.

This basic Data Space system was expanded by new features and services, that are based on the UNDERPIN partners software products, namely Ontotext’s GraphDB, SWC’s PoolParty Semantic Suite, ARC’s KnowDE, and finally AIT’s Smart Contracting system. The interplay and integration approach are described in the «UNDERPIN system architecture and components description» in full detail. The main goal of this expansion is to provide a “Data Space Semantic Layer” that enables (semantic) interoperability regarding the metadata and data inside the UNDERPIN Data Space, as well as with other relevant European Data Spaces. Additionally, this document provides a report on the status of the UNDERPIN Data Space deployment.

1 Introduction

This introduction section is split into two main areas: (i) a short introduction into the overall topic of Data Spaces and the UNDERPIN project as well as into the topic of this deliverable and (ii) the subsection “Relation to other work packages and deliverables” of the deliverable D2.2 on hand, to allow easy further reading of other deliverables. D2.2 is an updated and final version of the previously submitted D2.1.

1.1 Data Spaces – UNDERPIN – Deliverable D2.2

The field of Data Spaces is rapidly expanding, enabling secure and trusted data exchange within and across domains, which supports data trading and the growth of the European data economy. To stay informed about this area, the Data Space Radar Report [2] is recommended. Ongoing knowledge exchange, collaboration with international initiatives, and the adoption of new technologies are essential for the successful development of Data Spaces in Europe.

Through the UNDERPIN project, European manufacturers, their business ecosystems, governmental and public, research, and civil society stakeholders will be provided with a coherent Data Space solution that complies with EU standards and GAIA-X guidelines [3]. This solution will facilitate secure data sharing among partners and support data analysis to improve company operations. The UNDERPIN Data Space aims to ensure secure, trusted cross-organisational data sharing, focusing on both SMEs and large industry players to enhance products and services. One of UNDERPIN's objectives is to integrate its outcomes into the European Standardization landscape for Industrial Data Sharing. The goal is to develop pre-normative standards for stakeholder adoption and influence regulatory provisions enforcing these standards. WP 2 focuses on upgrading the Data Space using proven technologies and software components that adhere to IDSA and GAIA-X guidelines, standards, and recommendations, including semantic technologies, predictive maintenance, and analytics. UNDERPIN technology partners contribute ready-to-use technology and software with high TRL levels, successfully used in production by customers worldwide. Additional data management and analytics tools from the DataBri-X project will be integrated. The UNDERPIN cloud environment will be provided and operated by MOH, ensuring continued operations beyond the project. This technology approach enables interoperability within the Data Space and with other Data Spaces using the same methods, supporting the idea of a European-wide Data Space. This approach includes developing and integrating a Semantic Layer for Data Spaces.

Relation to other work packages and deliverables

1.2 Relation to other work packages and deliverables

This deliverable D2.2 refers to work already carried out and partly summarised in already submitted deliverables, as well as to work results carried out in the work packages: WP3 (Data Space Operational Infrastructure) and WP4 (Use cases for Data Space demonstration and validation). Moreover, it considers the results of WP5 (Business plan and sustainability) and WP6 (Communication, Dissemination and Scale Out), that are relevant for requirements elicitation and engineering.

The most important past deliverables to consider in relation with D2.2 are:

- D2.1 UNDERPIN requirements and enablers adaptation midterm report, review of relevant regulatory and standardization landscape, plan for implementation of pre-standardization activities, submitted in M9 (August 2024)
- D4.2a Use Case Validation & Lessons learnt, mid-term report, submitted in M12 (November 2024)
- D3.1 UNDERPIN Data Space infrastructure, mid-term deployment and integration report, submitted in M12 (November 2024)

The most important upcoming deliverables to consider in relation to D2.2 are:

- D3.2 UNDERPIN Data Space infrastructure, final deployment and integration report, to be submitted in M24 (November 2025)
- D4.2b Use Case Validation & Lessons learnt, final report, to be submitted in M24 (November 2025)
- D6.2 Communication, Exploitation, Dissemination and Pre-standardization Plan and Activities report (final), to be submitted in M24 (November 2025)

2 Requirements Elicitation and Specification

The Requirements Elicitation methodology followed in UNDRPIN is a structured, multi-stage process that progresses from gathering use cases to implementation. In Figure 1, the timeline and the stages are presented.

Figure 1. Requirements Engineering in UNDERPIN

The process of Requirements Elicitation and Specification was thoroughly described in the deliverable D2.1. During the period covered by this deliverable, M10-M18, we followed the same methodology and activities to update and finalize the requirements for the UNDERPIN Data Space.

In particular, an additional online technical workshop was held, covering the topics of a) smart contracts, b) Data Space metadata and c) time series analytics. The results of this workshop are discussed in the following section.

Furthermore, the series of the WP 2-3-4 calls (all technical WPs), were re-initiated and intensified from 3-weekly to bi-weekly and even weekly meetings for the period M11-M15, providing valuable input both for adding new requirements and for updating existing ones after the first phase of the deployment of the UNDERPIN Data Space infrastructure. The actual experience of deploying and testing the several components of which the Data Space is composed was invaluable in this process and allowed to further polish the requirements, based on the needs of both end-users and infrastructure providers.

In this section we provide the Use Cases and the Data Space requirements as those were finalized during the T2.2 and T2.3.

2.1 Use Case Requirements and Specification

This section provides the requirements from the perspective of the identified Use Cases. The process of identifying the use cases is described in D2.1. Here we present the final identified use cases along with the requirements for each.

Table 1: UNDERPIN use cases

Identifier	Title	Pilot
UC1.1	Monitoring and predictive maintenance in the refinery	Refinery
UC2.1	Predictive maintenance in wind farms	Wind farms
UC2.2	Wind turbine blade repair prediction	Wind farms

An overview of each individual use case is provided in the **Annex A** of this document. The reader should also consider the information provided in the deliverable D4.1: *Use case planning report* for a detailed description of each use case and its processes. To avoid duplication of information we have omitted D4.1 information and results here.

After the use cases were defined, a set of requirements was established for each use case, split into two categories:

- Business
- Functional

Due to the similar nature of the use cases and the shared organizational and operational procedures of the key stakeholders, a lot of the requirements are highly similar, however they are included in each use case for the sake of completeness.

2.1.1 UC1.1: Monitoring and predictive maintenance in the refinery

From the perspective of the refinery, the following business requirements emerge from this use case:

- Predictive maintenance: Develop a predictive maintenance procedure that will enable the streamlining of maintenance operations, minimizing downtime and costs.
- Equipment monitoring: Near real-time monitoring of equipment performance versus normal operating conditions to detect abnormal behaviour and apply corrective actions without interrupting operation.

In terms of functional requirements, the following key requirements have been identified:

- Data collection automation: Currently the data is manually downloaded from the DCS systems before entering the Data Space, which is not sufficient for the efficient implementation of the use case and needs to be automated. While this issue will most likely have to be solved within the user’s environment, it is included as a requirement as it highlights a potential issue that future stakeholders might also face.
- Streaming of data: The data from the refinery equipment will need to be streamed in hourly batches with a granularity of 5 mins to the predictive maintenance tool.
- Data pre-processing: A data cleaning procedure will need to be performed to identify and address errors in the datasets, such as inaccurate or incomplete data.
- Visualization: For the results of the predictive maintenance tool to turn into actionable information, they will need to be presented in a user interface/dashboard that can be accessed from the relevant parties (e.g., maintenance department) through relevant credentials.

An additional requirement for data anonymization has been identified, however, since anonymization needs sector-specific input and cannot easily be generalized, the intent is for it to be performed within the environment of the user before the data enters the Data Space.

2.1.2 UC2.1: Predictive maintenance in the wind farms

While this use case shares a lot of similarities with UC1.1, maintenance in the wind farms is not performed in-house, but instead through a contractor, which alters the business requirements from a user perspective:

- Maintenance benchmarking: Develop a predictive maintenance procedure that will allow the user to benchmark the quality of the maintenance services offered by the contractor.

In terms of functional requirements, the following key requirements have been identified:

- Data collection automation: Currently the data is manually downloaded from the SCADA systems before entering the Data Space, which is not sufficient for the efficient implementation of the use case and needs to be automated. While this issue will most likely have to be solved within the user's environment, it is included as a requirement as it highlights a potential issue that future stakeholders might also face.
- Streaming of data: The data from the wind farms will need to be streamed in daily batches with a granularity of 10 mins to the predictive maintenance tool. The frequency of the batches is subject to change, depending on the outcome of the previously described requirement.
- Data pre-processing: A data cleaning procedure will need to be performed to identify and address errors in the datasets, such as inaccurate or incomplete data.
- Visualization: For the results of the predictive maintenance tool to turn into actionable information, they will need to be presented in a user interface/dashboard that can be accessed from the relevant parties (e.g., maintenance department) through relevant credentials.

An additional requirement for data anonymization has been identified, however, since anonymization needs sector-specific input and cannot easily be generalized, the intent is for it to be performed within the environment of the user before the data enters the Data Space.

2.1.3 UC2.2: Wind turbine blade repair prediction

This use case acts as a subset of UC2.2 and largely shares the same requirements. The core, however, business requirement is somewhat different:

- Blade damage identification: Monitoring of the state of wind turbine blades and timely identification of potential blade damage using a predictive maintenance model, which will be used as feedback for ad hoc visual inspections.

The functional requirements are identical to those of UC2.1.

2.2 Data Space Requirements and Specification

This chapter provides the information about the UNDERPIN Data Space (core system) requirements identified via the different methodologies described in D2.1. We discuss functional and non-functional requirements for specific technical components based on the previously identified use cases.

UNDERPIN hereby fully follows the trends, recommendations and standards in place. These are dynamically developing in an emerging technology field. Namely the recommendations of:

- the International Data Space Association and the International Data Space recommendations [4]

- GAIA-X [5]
- the Eclipse Data Space Components [6]
- existing ISO Standards [7]
- W3C Recommendations [8]

The Infographic in Figure 2 is depicting the elements and components of an IDS-compliant Data Space. It represents a conceptual framework by the International Data Spaces Association for data exchange in a "Data Space." It outlines the structure and flow of data among various stakeholders, and the related technical components.

Figure 2. IDS typical Data Space Architecture (Source: IDSA)

2.2.1 Core Data Space Component Requirements

This section outlines the technical requirements for integrating, adapting and deploying various core Data Space components for the UNDERPIN project. As outlined above we follow the IDS architecture recommendations and building blocks to realize the Data Space.

According to the IDS-RAM 4.0, a Minimum Viable Data Space (MVDS) is composed of at least two Connectors and an Identity Provider (IdP). The IdP is the Data Space component which the other components on the Data Space are registered. Then the connector is the software component that implements the secure metadata and data exchange between the participants of the Data Space.

Thus, the fundamental requirement of the MVDS is that the connectors can communicate with each other through the Data Space Protocol and authenticate themselves using the IdP.

However, the requirements of the MVDS are just a Proof of Concept. For a sustainable and production-ready Data Space there are several other components needed to a) facilitate the administration of the Data Space and b) empower the Data Space participants with tools that would help them to utilize the Data Space.

2.2.1.1 Identity Provider

In the IDS-RAM 4.0, the IdP plays a central role in establishing trust and secure identity management within Data Spaces. According to IDS RAM 4.0, the IdP is responsible for the authentication and verification of participants in the IDS ecosystem. The key responsibilities of the IdP in IDS RAM 4.0:

1. Participant Identity Verification:
 - The IdP ensures that each participant in the Data Space (e.g., data providers, data consumers, broker) has a verified identity.
 - This verification process typically includes checking credentials and attributes issued by a Certification Body.
2. Token Issuance for Authentication:
 - The IdP issues JSON Web Tokens (JWTs) or similar tokens that participants use to authenticate themselves when interacting with other components in the IDS.
 - These tokens include verified identity information and security claims.
3. Integration with the Dynamic Attribute Provisioning Service (DAPS):
 - The IdP works closely with DAPS, which issues dynamic attribute tokens (DATs) based on identity information for enforcing access control in a fine-grained manner.
4. Enabling Secure Communications:
 - By managing identities and authentication tokens, the IdP contributes to establishing secure, trusted communication channels between IDS connectors and other components.

The following functional requirements have been identified for the IdP:

Table 2. Functional and Non-Functional Requirements of the IdP

Functional requirements	
Category	Requirement
Identity Verification	Verify participant identities using credentials issued by the Certification Body.
Token Issuance	Generate and issue cryptographically signed identity tokens (e.g., JWT) with claims and validity.
DAPS Integration	Collaborate with DAPS for DAT issuance and verification.
Revocation Management	Support token revocation and expiration handling.
	Provide status via CRL or OCSP.
Logging & Auditing	Record authentication events and identity verification steps in tamper-evident logs.
Attribute Management	Maintain and manage identity attributes (e.g., roles, org affiliation) with secure access controls.
Secure API Access	Provide HTTPS-protected APIs for identity and token services, with proper authentication and rate limits.
Non-Functional Requirements	
Category	Requirement
Security	Ensure cryptographic security. Protect against impersonation, replay, and token forgery attacks.
Availability	High availability (e.g., 99.9%) to ensure continuous access to identity services.
Performance	Low-latency identity verification and token issuance (e.g., <200ms response time).

Scalability	Scale to support many participants and simultaneous authentication requests.
Maintainability	Easily updateable and configurable. Include centralized monitoring/logging tools.
Interoperability	Conform to standard identity protocols
Usability	Provide clear admin interface for managing users, roles, certificates, and logs.
Auditability	Offer comprehensive logs for compliance and forensic analysis. Support traceability of events.
Portability	Deployable on different platforms; support containerization and orchestration tools (e.g., Docker, K8s).

2.2.1.2 Data Space Connector

The IDS Connector is the core technical component for trusted, sovereign, and interoperable data exchange between participants in a Data Space. It enforces data usage policies, ensures security and compliance, and provides standardized interfaces for data exchange. It serves as the "gatekeeper" of a participant's data, allowing:

- Control over what data is shared
- With whom it is shared
- Under what conditions it can be used

The functional and non-functional requirements for the Data Space connector are presented below.

Table 3. Functional and Non-Functional Requirements of the Data Space Connector

Functional Requirements	
Category	Requirement
Identity & Trust	Authenticate using IdP and DAPS.
	Possess valid certificates and tokens (DATs).
Policy Enforcement	Define, interpret, and enforce usage control policies defined in ODRL.
Interoperability	Implement IDS standard interfaces and protocols (Dataspace Protocol).
	Support IDS Information Model.
Secure Data Transmission	Use TLS 1.3 .
	Support mutual authentication.
	Ensure data integrity and confidentiality.
Provenance & Logging	Maintain tamper-proof logs.
	Trace all data transactions.
Connector Interfaces	Expose APIs for metadata exchange, contract negotiation, data provisioning/consumption.
Modularity & Extensibility	Modular architecture for policy engines, data models, and domain-specific logic.
Deployment Flexibility	Support deployment in cloud and on-premises environments.
	Support containerization (e.g., via Docker) and orchestration (e.g., Kubernetes).
Non-Functional Requirements	
Category	Requirement
Security	Ensure CIA (confidentiality, integrity, availability) .
	Resist attacks.

	Secure key storage.
Performance	Low-latency exchanges.
	Minimal policy enforcement overhead.
	Scalable data flow handling.
Availability	High uptime (e.g., >99.9%).
	Resilience to failures and retries.
Scalability	Support growing participant/data volume and negotiation complexity.
Maintainability	Easy updates and configuration.
	Monitoring/logging tools (e.g., Prometheus).
Interoperability	Conform to open standards.
	Integrate with external systems (e.g., ERP, analytics platforms).
Usability	Clear admin interfaces (UI/CLI/API).
	Actionable logs and messages.
Auditability	Verifiable logs for policy decisions and transactions.
	Non-repudiation via digital signatures.

2.2.1.3 Data Space Connector UI

The Data Space Connector UI is a web interface that supports Data Space participants on the various workflows of providing or consuming data or services within the Data Space. Although a connector can be still operated without a UI via APIs, using one benefits the user-friendliness and easy management of the connector.

Table 4. Functional and Non-Functional Requirements of the Data Space Connector UI

Functional Requirements	
Category	Requirement
User Authentication	Authenticate users using credentials managed by the IDS-compliant IdP.
Policy Configuration	Allow users to create, edit, and assign usage policies to data assets (e.g., via ODRL).
Asset Registration	UI for registering and describing data assets, including metadata, contracts, and endpoints.
Contract Offer Management	Visual interface to manage and review contract offers and agreements with other participants.
Monitoring & Logs	Display connector activity logs, health status, and data exchange metrics (may integrate with Prometheus/Grafana).
API Management	Provide settings for data APIs (e.g., URL mapping, access conditions).
Localization Support	(Optional) Support multiple languages for broader adoption across Data Space participants.
Usability Enhancements	Offer UX features like tooltips, validations, guided workflows, and search/filter capabilities.
Non-Functional Requirements	
Category	Requirement
Security	Enforce HTTPS; support OAuth2 secure token handling Validate user sessions. Prevent CSRF/XSS attacks.
Availability	Ensure high uptime (e.g., 99.9%) to support critical Data Space operations.
Performance	UI should load within <2s. Backend calls should complete in <500ms in typical scenarios.

Scalability	Support concurrent sessions for multiple connector users without degradation.
Maintainability	Modular and clean architecture for maintainability. CI/CD and containerized deployment recommended.
Interoperability	Work seamlessly with EDC APIs and external services like logging or monitoring tools.
Usability	Provide an intuitive, responsive UI. Follow accessibility and responsive design best practices.
Portability	Containerized (e.g., Docker) and deployable alongside the EDC Connector in cloud or on-prem environments.

2.2.1.4 Metadata Broker

The Metadata Broker in IDS acts as a directory service that allows participants to publish, discover, and query metadata about available data offerings in the Data Space — similar to a catalogue or registry but governed by IDS trust and interoperability principles.

Table 5. Functional and Non-Functional Requirements of the Metadata Broker

Functional Requirements	
Category	Requirement
Metadata Publication	Allow participants to register/publish metadata about available data resources, endpoints, and usage policies.
Search & Discovery	Provide search, filter, and query functionality to discover data offerings using IDS Information Model.
Standardized Interfaces	Support IDS standard protocols (e.g., IDS Dataspace Protocol) for metadata exchange.
Identity Verification	Authenticate and authorize participants using IdP and validate credentials (e.g., DATs).
Policy Awareness	Expose linked contract offers and usage policies along with metadata.
Metadata Validation	Validate submitted metadata against the IDS Information Model and required schema constraints.
Interoperability	Enable interoperability with other brokers, data catalogue systems, and IDS connectors.
Update & Deletion	Support participants in updating or removing published metadata securely.
Event Notification	Optionally notify subscribers about new or changed metadata entries.
Non-Functional Requirements	
Category	Requirement
Security	Ensure secure access to metadata via TLS. Enforce authentication and authorization for publication/discovery.
Availability	High availability (e.g., >99.9%) to enable continuous metadata access and publishing.
Performance	Fast query response times (e.g., <500ms for standard queries) Efficient handling of concurrent requests.
Scalability	Scale to accommodate growing numbers of participants, datasets, and queries.
Maintainability	Easy to configure and manage. Support logging, monitoring, and health checks.
Interoperability	Support standard metadata vocabularies (e.g., IDS Information Model, W3C DCAT, schema.org).
Usability	Provide a user-friendly API and/or web interface for metadata management and discovery.
Auditability	Maintain detailed logs of metadata publication and access

	Support audit trails.
Compliance	Ensure compliance with IDS policies, privacy regulations (e.g., GDPR), and organizational metadata policies.
Portability	Deployable in on-premises, edge, or cloud environments; support containers (Docker) and orchestration.

2.2.1.5 Vocabulary Hub

The IDS Vocabulary Hub plays a key role in enabling semantic interoperability across the Data Space. It allows participants to register, retrieve, and manage vocabularies, ontologies, and taxonomies that describe data and metadata in a machine-interpretable way, aligned with the IDS Information Model and linked data principles.

Table 6. Functional and Non-Functional Requirements of the Vocabulary Hub

Functional Requirements	
Category	Requirement
Vocabulary Publication	Allow participants and domain experts to publish and register vocabularies, taxonomies, and ontologies.
Vocabulary Retrieval	Provide standard APIs and web interfaces to query, browse, and retrieve vocabulary terms and definitions.
Versioning Support	Support versioning and change tracking for vocabularies to manage evolution over time.
Compliance Validation	Validate vocabularies for syntactic and semantic correctness (e.g., SHACL, OWL validation).
Semantic Alignment	Enable linking between vocabularies and concepts (e.g., SKOS mappings, equivalence declarations).
Identity Verification	Authenticate publishers and users to control vocabulary access and prevent unauthorized changes.
Interoperability	Support interoperability via standards like RDF, OWL, SKOS, and SPARQL endpoints.
Governance Support	Allow submission for review, approval, and curation workflows by domain or Data Space stewards.
Machine-Readable Access	Expose vocabularies as linked data with resolvable URIs and content negotiation (e.g., RDF/XML, Turtle, JSON-LD).
Non-Functional Requirements	
Category	Requirement
Security	Enforce secure access to the publishing and retrieval APIs using HTTPS, tokens, and access control.
Availability	Ensure high availability of vocabulary resolution and querying endpoints (e.g., >99.9% uptime).
Performance	Low latency for lookup and SPARQL query responses. Efficient ontology reasoning if applicable.
Scalability	Scalable to support thousands of terms, vocabularies, and concurrent users.
Maintainability	Easy vocabulary upload, update, and rollback. Support for curation workflows and change history.
Interoperability	Adhere to W3C and IDS vocabulary standards. Compatible with IDS Information Model and external tools.
Usability	Provide intuitive UIs and developer-friendly APIs for exploration, search, and integration.
Auditability	Keep records of all changes and accesses for vocabulary governance and compliance tracking.

Compliance	Follow FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable); align with IDS data governance rules.
Portability	Containerized deployment. Support for cloud installations. Integration with other IDS components.

2.2.1.6 Logging House

The Logging House is a component that ensures transparent, tamper-evident, and auditable tracking of events (such as data transactions, policy enforcement, and identity validations) across the Data Space. When backed by a blockchain ledger, it further enhances trust, immutability, and non-repudiation — critical for governance, dispute resolution, and regulatory compliance.

Table 7. Functional and Non-Functional Requirements of the Logging House

Functional Requirements	
Category	Requirement
Event Ingestion	Receive and record log entries from authorized IDS participants (mainly the connector).
Blockchain Integration	Maintain log entries on a blockchain ledger for tamper-evident, immutable storage.
Distributed Logging	Support distributed submission and replication of logs across multiple nodes or authorities.
Cryptographic Assurance	Sign log entries and ensure integrity using hash chaining, digital signatures, and timestamps.
Participant Authentication	Accept log entries only from authenticated, authorized participants (via DATs or equivalent credentials).
Query Interface	Provide secure APIs for querying logs based on criteria (e.g., event type, timestamp, participant).
Event Classification	Support multiple log types: policy enforcement, data access, identity verification, contract negotiation, etc.
Audit Trail Generation	Generate verifiable audit trails for IDS transactions, supporting dispute resolution and compliance audits.
Privacy-Preserving Logs	Support encryption, anonymization, or selective disclosure to comply with data protection laws (e.g., GDPR).
Interoperability	Interface with other IDS components and third-party audit or analytics systems.
Non-Functional Requirements	
Category	Requirement
Security	Ensure log confidentiality, integrity, and non-repudiation. Protect against unauthorized access and forgery.
Immutability	Once recorded, log entries must be unalterable — enforced by blockchain consensus and cryptographic proofs.
Availability	High uptime and redundancy across blockchain nodes. Must not become a single point of failure.
Performance	Efficient log ingestion and indexing. Optimize for high throughput use cases without sacrificing finality.
Scalability	Handle growing volumes of logs across many participants. Use scalable blockchain frameworks (e.g., Hyperledger, Besu).
Maintainability	Support monitoring, node synchronization, chain pruning/archiving if necessary.
Interoperability	Compatible with different blockchain platforms and IDS services (e.g., via smart contracts or standard APIs).

Usability	Offer clear APIs and possibly UIs for querying, visualizing, or exporting logs.
Auditability	Provide full, verifiable, timestamped audit trails. Logs must be legally admissible if needed.
Portability	Deployable across infrastructures. Support containerization and blockchain network configuration.

2.2.1.7 Data Space Administration

The administration of a Data Space is a complex undertaking, involving the meticulous management of diverse aspects to ensure efficiency and adherence to Data Space policies. It necessitates the registration and management of organizations, roles, users, connectors, and other pertinent IDS Data Space components on the IdP. Therefore, a centralized administrative component is essential. The requirements for such a Data Space Administration component are presented on Table 8.

Table 8. Functional and Non-Functional Requirements of the Data Space Administration

Functional Requirements	
Category	Requirement
Organization Onboarding	Allow the service operator to register/invite organizations into the Data Space.
Organization Self-Management	Enable organization admins to manage their users and roles within their own scope.
Connector Registration	Allow organizations to register their own EDC Connectors or request managed connectors from the Service Operator.
Managed Connector Provisioning	Enable Service Operator to register and provision managed connectors, including metadata and certificate creation.
Certificate Management	Provide interface to create or register connector certificates on the IdP.
Role-Based Access Control	Enforce differentiated permissions for Service Operators, Org Admins, and Org Users and Data Space Operator.
Asset Discovery Interface	Provide a searchable UI for users to discover shared assets via metadata from the Metadata Broker.
Filtered Search	Enable users to apply filters (e.g., provider, category, license type) to asset search.
Metadata Presentation	Present asset metadata (from broker) in a human-readable format, including policies and contract information if available.
Non-Functional Requirements	
Category	Requirement
Security	Enforce OAuth2 authentication; protect all endpoints via HTTPS; support role-based access controls.
Multi-Tenancy	Support isolation of data and permissions across different organizations within the same Data Space.
Availability	Ensure high uptime for business-critical administration functions (e.g., >99.9%).
Performance	Fast search/filter interaction (<500ms), responsive UI (<2s), scalable to many organizations.
Usability	Provide a clean, intuitive user interface for both technical and non-technical users.
Maintainability	Modular architecture; container-based deployment (e.g., Docker); CI/CD support.
Interoperability	Compatible with EDC Connectors, IDS Metadata Broker, Certificate Authorities, and OAuth2 providers.

Auditability	Log all sensitive actions (e.g., connector provisioning, user changes) and retain for auditing.
Compliance	Respect GDPR and other data governance principles; store no unnecessary personal data.
Extensibility	Allow future integration of contract negotiation, analytics, or federation features.
Portability	Deployable in cloud, on-premises, or hybrid environments.

2.2.1.8 Data Space Landing Page

The UNDERPIN Landing Page serves as a central hub for the UNDERPIN Data Space. It offers access to Data Space Components, along with related APIs. Users can find detailed information, URLs, and brief descriptions of each component, as well as access details for connectors, including owner organizations and contact information. The page also provides how-to guides for Data Providers, consumers, and Service Providers, general project information, FAQs, contact details, and onboarding assistance. In contrast to the Authority Portal, which is a protected component for authorized members, the Landing Page is a public facing component, aimed to advertise the Data Space and drive interested organizations into the UNDERPIN Data Space through the onboarding procedure.

Table 9. Functional and Non-Functional Requirements of the Data Space Landing Page

Functional Requirements	
Category	Requirement
Component Index	Provide a table listing all key UNDERPIN components with their URLs and brief descriptions/intended use.
Connector Index	Offer a table listing of connectors with their URLs, owner organizations, and contact information for each owner.
Technology Index	Include a table detailing the underlying technologies used, their descriptions/intended use, developer information, and links to DPP (Data Privacy Policy) details where applicable.
How-To Guides	Provide step-by-step guides (with screenshots) and/or path diagrams for different user roles (Data Provider, Data Consumer, Service Provider) for common workflows like creating/adding assets, discovering/receiving assets, and using services.
General Project Information	Display the purpose of the UNDERPIN Data Space, its intended user base (energy and manufacturing predictive maintenance), description of the Data Space custodian, hosting details, and information about the funding project/consortium.
FAQ Section	Include a Frequently Asked Questions section with answers that may link to other parts of the landing page or Data Space components.
Contact Information	Provide contact information for the Data Space custodian and/or a contact form. Offer ways to get help with onboarding based on user roles.
Search Functionality (Optional)	Implement a search bar on the landing page to allow users to quickly find specific information.
Non-Functional Requirements	
Category	Requirement Description
Template & Layout	Use the Keen Bootstrap template. Adopt a light theme with a dark sidebar. The homepage should resemble a dashboard with links to content sections arranged in a grid.
Sidebar Navigation	The sidebar must list all content sections and subcomponents, providing easy navigation. It should have minimize toggle, be hoverable, and not be minimized by default.

Header	The header content should display the page title.
Responsiveness	The landing page should be fully responsive and work well on various screen sizes and devices (desktops, tablets, mobile phones).
Performance	The page should load quickly and efficiently. Optimize images and code for fast loading times.
Security	Implement security measures to protect the landing page and any sensitive information it displays.
Maintainability	Code and content should be structured and organized for easy updates and maintenance in the future.
Cross-Browser Compatibility	The landing page should function correctly in all major web browsers (Chrome, Firefox, Safari, Edge).

2.2.2 Value Added services

2.2.2.1 Structured Data Modeller

The Structured Data Modeller tool is designed to facilitate the detailed description and management of data assets within a Data Space. It provides a user interface and backend services for Data Providers to input, store, and publish rich metadata about their datasets. This includes information about the dataset itself, the structure of the data (CSVW), and specific characteristics of individual columns. The Structured Data Modeller is crucial for several reasons:

1. **Enhanced Data Discovery and Search:** Detailed metadata enables Data Consumers to easily find and understand relevant datasets. By describing sensor types, devices, units, and other characteristics, the tool supports rich dataset search and filtering. This is essential for Data Consumers who need specific data to train models or conduct analyses.
2. **Improved Data Level Interoperability:** By providing structured and standardised descriptions of data, the tool significantly improves data level interoperability within the Data Space. When all datasets follow a consistent schema and use controlled vocabularies, different Data Consumers and applications can seamlessly integrate and process the data. This reduces the effort required to understand and use datasets from various providers.
3. **Facilitated Data Consumption and Automation:** Machine-readable metadata allows Data Consumers to automate their data consumption processes. For example, they can use metadata to provision InfluxDB ingestion or to write generic predictive analytics applications. This eliminates manual effort and improves efficiency.
4. **Support for Data Storage Options:** The tool provides backend support for storing raw data files on a file server ("data lake") and for ingesting CSV data into a time series database (e.g., InfluxDB). This offers flexibility to Data Providers and Consumers in how data is stored and accessed. Data Consumers can directly query the time series database to retrieve specific data points instead of downloading entire files, thus improving efficiency.
5. **Backend Endpoints for EDC Connectors:** The tool's backend provides API endpoints that EDC connectors can use to retrieve asset and metadata information. This ensures that all relevant data and its description are available to the Data Space infrastructure and participants. The support of additional fields, classes, and non-payloads (e.g., CSVW and other RDF property definitions) makes it possible to provide a rich description of the data.
6. **Enabling Data Quality:** By standardising metadata, the tool supports the improvement of data quality over time.

In summary, the Structured Data Modeller is a core component for any Data Space aiming for effective data sharing and interoperability. It empowers Data Providers to thoroughly describe their data and enables Data Consumers to easily discover, understand, and utilise the data in automated and efficient ways.

Table 10. Functional and Non-Functional Requirements of the Structured Data Modeller

Functional Requirements	
Category	Requirement
Metadata Entry	Data Providers should be able to input and save asset details, including asset name and description.
Column Management	The tool should allow dynamic column management to add, edit, and remove columns from the description of an asset.
Column Details	Data Providers should be able to input detailed information for each column (e.g., name, characteristics, etc.).
Metadata Generation	The tool should generate CSVW metadata, along with other vocabularies such as DCV, based on the column details provided.
Preview & Submit	The tool should provide a preview section to summarise the input data and a submit button to finalise the asset description.
Template Selection	Data Providers should be able to select from existing templates for asset structure definitions.
Template Customization	The tool should allow users to customise selected templates to fit their specific needs.
Template Saving	Users should be able to save their customised templates for future use.
CSV Introspection	The tool should be able to introspect a CSV file and extract draft metadata, including column names, column kind (timestamp, string, numeric), timestamp range, and characteristics for each numeric column.
Raw Data Storage	The tool should support storing raw data (e.g., CSV files) on a file server/space ("data lake"). Each Provider should have separate access to their storage space.
Time series Ingestion	The tool should support the ingestion of CSV data into a time series database (e.g., InfluxDB). Users should be able to choose an asset to be included as part of a specific time series on the database
EDC Endpoints	The backend should provide API endpoints that EDC connectors can use to retrieve asset and metadata information.
Validation	The tool should be able to validate that a slice conforms to the Table Schema of a Series. There should be validation rules to ensure modifications to the schema adhere to predefined standards and validation to enforce the use of controlled vocabulary terms.
Non-Functional Requirements	
Category	Requirement
User Experience	The interface should be intuitive and easy to use. The editor should enhance user experience with tooltips and contextual help for each input field.
Semantic Standards	The generated metadata should comply with semantic standards, specifically CSVW for the description of the structure of datasets.
Reusability	The tool should enable reusability of column names and descriptions between datasets (normalization, synonym replacement).
Data Access	The tool should be able to access CSV files from a file server/space ("data lake") and parse them based on the structure definition provided.

2.2.2.2 File Storage

In the context of an IDSA-compliant Data Space, Connectors serve as decentralized intermediaries that enable standardized data exchange without storing or centralizing data. The connectors ensure interoperability between participants through common interfaces and protocols focused on metadata exchange. Designed for flexibility, Connectors can integrate with diverse data infrastructures—including data lakes, sensor networks, and SCADA systems—via a modular "plug-in" architecture, minimizing disruption to existing environments.

Despite this, adoption challenges persist, especially around direct system integration due to security and operational concerns. As a result, many Data Providers opt to share data extracts (data dumps) instead of allowing real-time access.

To address these challenges and ease onboarding, the UNDERPIN Data Space includes a central File Storage service as a value-added option. This service allows participants to upload and share data without requiring immediate Connector integration, thus lowering technical barriers and enabling broader participation while maintaining core principles of data sovereignty and controlled access.

Table 11. Functional and Non-Functional Requirements of the File Storage Service

Functional	
Category	Requirement Description
Data Storage	The file server must be able to store raw data files.
S3 Compliance	The file server should be compliant with the S3 (Simple Storage Service) API, allowing for interaction with tools and applications that use this standard.
API Endpoints	The file server should provide backend API endpoints that EDC connectors can use to retrieve asset and metadata information.
Data Access	It should allow for data retrieval by authorized users or systems.
Non-Functional	
Category	Requirement Description
Security	It should be securable with Keycloak for authentication and authorization. Access to data should be controlled based on user roles and permissions. An ISMS (Information Security Management System) should be implemented. ISO/IEC 27001 and 27002 standards are relevant and should be considered.
Performance	It should provide efficient data storage and retrieval.
Scalability	The storage capacity should be scalable to accommodate growing data volumes.
Availability	The file server should be highly available and reliable.

2.2.2.3 Time Series Storage

UNDERPIN Data offers a tailored database solution for managing timeseries data, excelling in both its persistent storage capabilities and its advanced querying functionalities. This integration removes the common bottleneck of needing to download substantial volumes of data before any meaningful analysis can commence. Instead, users can directly interact with the data repository through a sophisticated query language equipped to handle a wide spectrum of analytical operations, from simple filtering and aggregation to more intricate temporal manipulations and pattern recognition.

While timeseries datasets can often be characterized by a multitude of recorded parameters, represented as numerous columns, the reality of analytical workflows often dictates a focus on specific subsets of this information. UNDERPIN Data addresses this inherent need for selectivity by providing comprehensive datasets, thus empowering users with the flexibility to extract precisely the columns and rows relevant to their immediate analytical objectives. This capability significantly enhances the inherent value and versatility of the stored data, making it suitable for a far broader range of analytical applications without the cumbersome necessity of maintaining and managing multiple, potentially redundant, distinct datasets.

This strategic approach to data management through services for in-database querying and targeted retrieval yields several key advantages. It fundamentally streamlines the process of data access, eliminating the delays and complexities associated with data staging and preparation. Furthermore, it contributes to tangible cost reductions by minimizing the resources required for data storage and transfer. The enforcement of consistency and standardization in analytical processes is another crucial benefit, as all analyses are performed against a single, authoritative source of truth.

Beyond these advantages, the ability to perform targeted data retrieval through sophisticated querying mechanisms directly translates to a minimization of data transfer volumes. This reduction in network traffic leads to demonstrably faster query execution times, as less data needs to be moved and processed. The optimized data handling also contributes to reduced overall storage requirements, as unnecessary data duplication is avoided. Collectively, these factors contribute to a significant improvement in overall operational efficiency, allowing analysts and data scientists to spend less time on data wrangling and more time on extracting meaningful insights.

The resulting granular access to timeseries data fosters a more focused and efficient analytical environment, accelerating the time-to-insight by allowing users to quickly isolate and examine the specific data points of interest. This prevents the cognitive overload that can occur when dealing with massive, undifferentiated datasets, enabling more effective pattern discovery and informed decision-making.

Table 12. Functional and Non-Functional Requirements of the Timeseries Storage

Functional Requirements	
Category	Description
Data Management	Support persistent storage of timeseries data.
Data Management	Enable advanced querying of timeseries data.
Data Management	Allow filtering and aggregation of timeseries data.
Data Management	Support intricate temporal manipulations and pattern recognition in queries.
Data Management	Provide access to comprehensive datasets.
Data Access	Allow users to extract specific columns and rows from datasets.
Data Access	Enable direct interaction with the data repository through a query language.
Non-Functional Requirements	
Category	Description
Performance	Minimize the need to download substantial volumes of data for analysis.
Performance	Ensure fast query execution times.

Performance	Minimize data transfer volumes.
Scalability	Handle large volumes of time series data.
Cost Efficiency	Minimize resources required for data storage and transfer.
Data Integrity	Ensure consistency and standardization in analytical processes.
Usability	Provide a query language that is user-friendly for data analysts and scientists.
Efficiency	Streamline the process of data access, eliminating delays and complexities of data staging and preparation.

2.2.2.4 Data Visualizer

UNDERPIN data visualizer is a web-based application designed to present and explore data related to various use cases, initially focusing on "UC2 Windfarm: Data Exploration" "UC1 Refinery Predictions" and "UC2 Windfarm Predictions". The primary goal is to offer users clear, interactive visualizations of both raw and processed data, facilitating informed decision-making.

The visualizer leverages a modern tech stack for a performant and user-friendly experience. The frontend is built using React and Vite, ensuring fast bundling and optimized performance. JavaScript is the primary language, with MobX managing the application state, providing automatic reactivity for seamless updates. React Router handles navigation between different sections of the dashboard. The user interface is constructed using the Ant Design library, offering elegant, responsive, and customizable components, adhering to a clean and minimalistic design principle. Charts and graphs are rendered using the React-ApexCharts library, enabling the clear display of various datasets and analysis results, with the potential for interactive elements to enhance user engagement.

Security is ensured, with authentication and authorization handled through seamless integration with the Data Space Keycloak instance. This is achieved using the keycloak-js library, ensuring secure Single Sign-On (SSO) and shared user credentials with the Authority Portal for efficient user management. The application connects to InfluxDB to retrieve timeseries data, which is crucial for real-time analytics and monitoring, particularly for use cases like windfarm and refinery predictions. The Axios library is employed for promise-based HTTP communication, ensuring efficient and reliable data retrieval even with large volumes of time-sensitive data.

The visualizer features a responsive layout, built on a responsive grid system, guaranteeing an optimal viewing experience across a wide range of devices, from desktops to tablets and mobile phones. This ensures accessibility and usability regardless of the user's preferred device. In essence, this Data Space visualizer will serve as a critical tool for understanding complex datasets and analysis outcomes within the UNDERPIN Data Space, empowering users with actionable insights through intuitive and secure data exploration.

Table 13. Functional and Non-Functional Requirements of the Data Visualizer

Functional Requirements	
Category	Description
Data Visualization	Display selected raw and processed datasets in various chart and graph formats.
Analysis Results Visualization	Present the results of data analysis processes in a clear and understandable manner, potentially including interactive filtering or drill-down.

Authentication via Data Space Keycloak	Allow users to securely log in to the dashboard using their Data Space Keycloak credentials.
Integration with InfluxDB	Establish a connection to InfluxDB to query and retrieve relevant timeseries data for visualization.
Navigation	Enable users to navigate between different main pages of the dashboard (e.g., UC1 Refinery Predictions, UC2 Windfarm Predictions, Data Exploration).
Non-Functional Requirements	
Category	Description
User-Friendly Interface	Clean, minimalistic, and intuitive design that is easy to navigate and understand for all users.
Responsive Layout	Seamless adaptation to different screen sizes and devices (desktops, tablets, mobile).
Performance	Fast loading and efficient display of data visualizations, even with large datasets.
Security	Ensure secure authentication and authorization through Keycloak integration, protecting access to sensitive data
Reliability	Stability and consistent availability for users.
Maintainability	Well-structured codebase and documented to facilitate future updates and maintenance.

2.3 Overarching Requirements

This section outlines the fundamental requirements for the UNDERPIN project, ensuring consistency, security, and compliance across all components. These overarching requirements are crucial for the successful deployment and integration of the system, as well as adherence to industry standards and data protection regulations.

2.3.1 Deployment and Integration

Each UNDERPIN component should be containerized using Docker [9]. This approach will facilitate scalable and flexible deployment in cloud environments. Communication between components must be secured using HTTPS, with appropriate authentication mechanisms such as OAuth2.0 [10] and JSON Web Tokens [11]. Furthermore, each service must implement comprehensive logging and monitoring capabilities to ensure high availability and rapid issue resolution.

2.3.1.1 CI/CD

To achieve robust and efficient automated deployment within CI/CD workflows, meticulous configuration of each UNDERPIN component's Docker container is paramount. This necessitates the inclusion of comprehensive and well-documented scripts or configuration files that facilitate the seamless automation of building, rigorous testing, and reliable deployment processes across diverse target environments (e.g., development, staging, production). These scripts should cover all critical stages of the deployment lifecycle, including image building, unit and integration testing, vulnerability scanning, environment-specific configuration management, and the actual deployment to the designated environment.

2.3.1.2 Container Orchestration

Furthermore, the adoption of container orchestration platforms such as Kubernetes or Docker Swarm is strongly recommended. These platforms provide essential capabilities for the effective management of the containers throughout their lifecycle, including automated deployment,

intelligent scaling based on resource utilization and demand, robust self-healing mechanisms to ensure high availability, and simplified management of network resources and storage. The chosen orchestration platform should be carefully configured to align with the specific requirements and scalability needs of the Data Space.

2.3.1.3 Authorization Protocols

For a unified and secure user authentication experience across the entire Data Space, UNDERPIN components must be designed for seamless integration with the central IdP. This centralized approach simplifies user management, enhances security posture, and provides a consistent experience for users accessing different components. To achieve this integration, components should adhere to industry-standard authentication and authorization protocols like OpenID Connect (OIDC) or Security Assertion Markup Language (SAML) for secure communication with the IdP.

2.3.1.4 Single Sign On

The configuration of each UNDERPIN component should include the necessary parameters to establish trust and securely validate authentication tokens issued by the central IdP. This ensures that a user authenticated by one component is automatically recognized and authorized to access other components within the Data Space without requiring authentication. This Single Sign-On (SSO) capability significantly reduces the overhead associated with managing authentication independently in each component, improves user convenience, and strengthens the overall security framework of the Data Space. Comprehensive documentation outlining the configuration process for integrating with the central IdP should be provided for each UNDERPIN component.

2.3.1.5 Logging

Beyond simply recording events, comprehensive logging for each service should capture a wide range of data points, including request/response details, error messages with stack traces, performance metrics like latency and resource utilization (CPU, memory, network I/O), security-related events (authentication attempts, authorization failures), and audit trails of significant system changes. This detailed logging is crucial for not only diagnosing the root cause of issues swiftly but also for proactive monitoring and trend analysis.

2.3.1.6 Monitoring

Monitoring capabilities should encompass real-time dashboards providing a holistic view of service health and performance indicators. These dashboards should be customizable and offer alerting mechanisms to notify relevant teams of anomalies or breaches of predefined thresholds.

2.3.2 Compliance and Standards

All components must comply with relevant data protection regulations, including GDPR [12], and adhere to industry best practices for secure software development and deployment. The software should be designed with scalability, maintainability, and security in mind.

3 UNDERPIN Data Space System Architecture and Enablers Adaptation

3.1 System Architecture Overview

The UNDERPIN system architecture covers the requirements above and provides a technological basis for the implementation of use cases and components. We note that the IDS components to form the IDS system layer architecture are seamlessly integrated into the overall system architecture. However, there are services which are not involved in the IDS-based data sharing, and which are therefore not part of the IDS system layer.

Figure 3. UNDERPIN System Architecture

We describe the components and services shown in the system architecture grouped by i) IDS components (shown in orange colour in the architecture diagram), ii) UNDERPIN Data Space services (shown in blue colour in the architecture diagram) and iii) the time series database (shown as a database icon in the right top of the architecture diagram).

3.1.1 IDS Components

Here we describe the basic IDS-RAM 4.0 compliant components of the UNDERPIN Data Space.

- Connector:** The IDS connectors implement the data exchange via the exposed data endpoints. They form the actual Data Space with a decentralized approach for data sharing and enable and enforce data sovereignty by means of contractual agreements between a Data Provider and a Data Consumer. UNDERPIN uses the EDC-CE [13]

connector implementation provided by Sovity GmbH, an EDC based connector, and extend it as needed by the project requirements. In addition, UNDERPIN integrates smart contracts into the connectors to enable logging capabilities for documenting events and actions associated with data exchange. This is further explained below at Logging House.

- **Identity Provider:** Identity and access management are a mandatory part of the Data Space to implement access control for data sharing. UNDERPIN uses a KeyCloak-based solution, namely the Sovity DAPS [14], which covers the necessary project requirements regarding authentication. Remark: This component is not shown on the diagram, but all IDS components are using it to retrieve DATs, to facilitate the authentication of each participant
- **Metadata Broker:** the metadata Broker, which is a connector itself, provides endpoints for registration, publication, maintenance, and query of asset metadata, called Self-Descriptions. The Broker is a central service on the IDS system layer, but contains metadata only, while data sharing is done mutually between two Connectors. UNDERPIN uses the metadata Broker provided by Sovity, namely the Catalog Crawler [15], extending it by adding graph-based metadata management and search based on Semantic Web standards.
- **Vocabulary Hub:** a central service which provides vocabularies and ontologies as a common basis for interoperability. This component is also a connector itself, acting as a gateway to a Vocabulary and Ontology Management System. UNDERPIN establishes PoolParty [16], provided by SWC, as a Vocabulary Hub, which covers the necessary functionality with a rich set of vocabulary and ontology management features and exposes the descriptions via a SPARQL endpoint.
- **Logging House:** the Logging House is a central logging facility to be able to track data sharing actions within the Data Space and to provide billing information. UNDERPIN introduces a Smart Contract implementation as a component to cover the Logging House functionality. By integrating Smart Contracts into the connectors, we can automatically log actions, like the establishment of a contractual agreement or the exchange of data, to the central Logging House.

3.1.2 Data Space Services

UNDERPIN introduces several services (described below) for implementing the use cases. To make these services available as part of the trusted IDS Data Space, we introduce Service Provider Connectors, which expose the service functionality via Web APIs. We identify two services to be exposed.

- **Predictive Maintenance:** these are services used to train and infer predictive maintenance models. We need to establish trusted access for Data Space participants, who send shared training data to these services.
- **Semantic Layer:** the Semantic Layer is a set of unified services to enable semantic interoperability in Data Spaces. It is based on the Vocabulary Hub component to provide data descriptions, consolidation and integration to make it easier for participants to make best use of the data available in a Data Space.

3.1.3 End User Apps

Other than the standard IDS components and the Data Space Services, UNDERPIN Data Space offers other End User Applications with the scope improve the UX of the participants:

3.1.3.1 Authority Portal and Data Catalogue

The Authority Portal is a central management system for authorities and Data Space members, providing oversight of the platform, participant management, and ensuring compliance with Data Space policies and regulations. UNDERPIN uses the Authority Portal, or as it is rebranded currently the Data Space Portal [17], provided by Sovity. The Authority Portal is an open-source Software as a Service (SaaS) solution designed to streamline the management of a Data Space. This innovative tool serves as a comprehensive Data Space Administration Tool, offering a platform where Data Space Administrators can seamlessly invite organizations and their users to participate in the Data Space. The Authority Portal is not just about managing participants. It also provides multiple avenues to add or acquire connectors and service partners. Additionally, other IDS components can be registered on the Data Space through the Authority Portal such as the Broker or the Vocabulary Hub.

The Data Catalogue (Broker) UI is integrated within the Authority Portal, allowing users to utilize both the Authority Portal and Data Catalogue seamlessly in one location. The Data Catalogue is exclusively available to Data Space members, thereby enhancing the benefits of their membership. Access to the Data Catalogue requires registered membership through the Authority Portal. The backend of the Data Catalogue uses the same connectors registry of the Authority Portal to harvest metadata, their catalogue entries, from each connector. However, there are some limitations of the current UI:

1. It is not configurable, thus custom facets are not visible/usable.
2. It uses the default RDBMS to execute the queries, thus although the actual catalog descriptions use an RDF data model, the expressivity of it is lost.

To this end, UNDERPIN extended the Catalog Crawler component by providing an extension responsible for ingesting the raw catalogue descriptions in RDF on a triplestore (GraphDB provided by OT). GraphDB has advanced search capabilities through the integration with enterprise-ready search engines such as Elasticsearch, enabling scalable, enhanced and complex querying. Details about the new search component are provided next.

3.1.3.2 UNDERPIN Semantic Search Application

A new search component was developed to facilitate the advanced Semantic Faceted Metadata Search Application of UNDERPIN. In regards of flexibility, there was a decision not to modify the current UI and relevant backend components of the Catalog Crawler. Instead, we developed a lightweight extension for the Catalog Crawler with the role of routing catalog/asset metadata to an external service. By design, the heavy lifting of processing the entries and handle the ingestion is performed on the external service.

As seen on Figure 4 , when a connector is harvested from the Catalog Crawler, the extension forwards the payload to the Metadata Ingester service. This service sanitizes the payload because the current version of the EDC-CE connector used (v10.4.2) might produce invalid RDF (missing or invalid JSON-LD context, local identifiers etc). Then the sanitized payload is stored in GraphDB.

The metadata ingester uses a dedicated repository and each connector's catalog is ingested on a dedicated named graph.

Figure 4. Metadata flow in the scope of the Search Component

This strategy allows for efficient handling of catalog updates. Other than the connectors' catalog metadata, this repository stores data from the Vocabulary Hub. Thus, any references to elements of Schemas, Vocabularies and Ontologies are queryable to allow advanced semantic search. Finally, GraphDB is configured to populate a connected index in Elasticsearch to power the Semantic Search Component. Finally, a new frontend component was developed to allow users to search across the available asset offers. Only authenticated users have access to this frontend, reusing the IdP of the Data Space. Through the UI, Data Consumers can search the catalogs of the Data Space by using free text search, or the faceted search filters, tailored to the needs of UNDERPIN. In addition to the search functionality, UNDERPIN provides recommendations based on the user defined query. This is powered by knowDE (knowledge-based recommendations) tool from project partner ARC, a semantic search assistant into the Semantic Search component.

3.1.3.3 UNDERPIN Data Vault Application

As discussed in the previous section, a Data Space Connector is not supposed to hold or store any data. Its purpose is to facilitate access to data that is provided by a variety of data backends such as REST APIs, databases or file storages. UNDERPIN provides a service called Data Vault, through which the Data Space participants can store data on a secure file storage which can then be shared through the participant's connector in the Data Space. In addition to this, in the case of CSV files, which is typical for measurement dumps, users can use the Structure Definition Editor, a component of the Data Vault application, to model their data, providing extensive description of the contents of each column in a CSV file. Finally, the Data Vault integrates with InfluxDB, a time series database as an alternative backend for data provision in the Data Space.

o S3 MinIO File Storage

MinIO is a high-performance, software-defined object storage solution designed for cloud-native environments, particularly Kubernetes. It features complete API compatibility with Amazon S3, enabling seamless integration into existing workflows. MinIO excels in handling large-scale unstructured data for AI/ML, big data analytics, and backups. Its Kubernetes-native design allows for easy deployment, management, and scaling within clusters, ensuring high throughput and low latency for demanding

workloads. This makes MinIO a versatile alternative for organizations seeking efficient and scalable object storage.

Data Vault integrates with MinIO to allow the Data Space participants store their data on dedicated buckets. Each participant organization has access only to their assigned bucket which they can use to upload data. Users are authenticated on the service using the same IdP of the Data Space providing an SSO experience. The storage service can accept any kind of file type.

- **UNDERPIN Structure Definition Editor**

In case an uploaded file is a CSV file, the Structure Definition Editor is available. This component of the Data Vault allows users to define the structure of their data, thus increasing data-level interoperability. At first, the user is required to define characteristics of the CSV “dialect” used on the uploaded file. This contains information about the separator used, encoding, the presence of headers and any other useful information that would be essential for successfully parsing the CSV file. Beyond this, on a next step, users can define the description of the columns of the CSV. This includes metadata with regard to the title of the column, its position on the CSV, the datatype and potentially a format of the value including patterns, as well as useful information about other characteristics of the particular column. The final structure definition is stored using the CSVW Vocabulary in RDF and is made available as part of the metadata of the specific file.

- **Integration with InfluxDB**

To further facilitate efficient processing and querying of data through Data Space, InfluxDB, a time series database, is available. Data Vault can be used to ingest data from CSV files managed through Data Vault to an InfluxDB instance. Data Vault utilizes the provided Structure Definition of the CSV file to drive the automated ingestion process. Influx has two query languages: Flux for functional-style processing and querying, and InfluxQL for declarative querying in the style of SQL. Flux offers over 400 functions for all kinds of data manipulation [18], including moving averages, windowing, derivatives, integration with machine learning, etc.

- **Sharing data on the Data Space**

When a user decides to share an asset stored in the Data Vault to the Data Space, a specific Data Address object should be defined and registered on the connector, as part of the metadata of the asset offer, in order to enable the successful exchange of data. In the case of S3-based Data Sink, the relevant data-plane of the connector, other than the address of this object, expects credentials that would give access to the specified resource. To this end, the Data Vault assists the users, by automatically generating the Data Address object, that can be registered on the connector. Data Vault, upon request, generates read-only credentials for the specific object on the participants bucket, which are presented on the metadata of the provided Data Address. In all cases, the Data Vault is not involved on the data transfer process, the data-plane has direct access to the integrated MinIO instance. The same feature is available for time series stored in InfluxDB.

3.2 Report on final Enablers Adaptation and Integration

Based on the existing embryonic Data Space at MOH that was already in place before the UNDERPIN project, the requirements engineering carried out in the requirements specification process and the experience from the initial deployment of the Data Space, the final requirements

are described in detail in this document. Based on this, the provision and development of the UNDERPIN Data Space enablers has progressed over the reported status on D2.1 that was submitted in M9, August 2024.

In the first phase of the UNDERPIN Data Space, a test bed using Connectors hosted by Sovity one their CaaS (Connectors as a Service) system was provided. Along with the connectors, the other essential components of the Data Space like the IdP and the Authority Portal, where also hosted by Sovity. As stated in D2.1, the plan was to move this infrastructure to the consortium's own premises. After consideration and having in mind the costs involved in such deployment the consortium decided on a self-managed Kubernetes environment, provided by Hetzner Online GmbH, to become the testing and production environment of UNDERPIN.

The Kubernetes cluster hosts the common IDS components such as the Authority Portal, the IdP, the Logging House, the Metadata Broker and the Vocabulary Hub. In addition, all value-added and accompanying services such as the Semantic Search, MinIO, InfluxDB, ElasticSearch, GraphDB, the Data Visualization Dashboard etc are also deployed on the same cluster. Several connectors are deployed on dedicated servers, one for each Use Case partner and a set of testing/development connectors.

Due to a license change on the EDC-CE connector provided by Sovity GmbH, in particular the license was changed from Apache-2.0 to Elastic License 2.0, it is not anymore allowed to provide the connector as a managed service without a special agreement. To this end, the consortium acquired a special license from Sovity GmbH in order to be able to continue to offer the deployed connectors to third parties, during the UNDERPIN project. Currently there are three options to have a connector on the UNDERPIN Data Space:

1. Managed and Hosted by the UNDERPIN consortium
2. Managed and Hosted by Sovity GmbH using their Connector-as-a-Service
3. Self-Host deployment on premises

The integration and further development of all components is a continuous process (following an agile continuous development and integration approach), where the Data Space basic system (Sovity community edition), the Connector as a Service ecosystem (CaaS), the UNDERPIN specific Data Space components (Semantic Layer) and the Use Case components (Time Series Database) are integrated and tested and provided for production and use in release cycles (iterations).

4 Conclusion

Deliverable D2.2 provides a comprehensive overview of the UNDERPIN Data Space's current status, including technical specifications and component integration. The requirements elicitation process has been thoroughly described in D2.1. The use case requirements and specification details are available in the previously submitted Deliverable D4.1.

The technical requirements identified and specified show a clear path along the European-wide (and beyond) developments of Data Spaces, namely following IDS architecture principles and EDC implementations. The UNDERPIN Data Space is built upon the EDC / Sovity IDS compliant components, that ensure always up-to-date Data Space Connectors available for UNDERPIN in a dynamically developing environment.

This basic Data Space ecosystem – that is the basis to develop from the existing embryonic Data Space into a full fledged European Data Space for manufacturing – is expanded by new features and services, that are based on the partners software products, namely OT's GraphDB, SWC's PoolParty Semantic Suite, and ARC's knowDE, and finally AIT's Smart Contracting system. The basis system, the additional components and integration work is already in place providing a fully functional Data Space.

Deliverable D2.2 provides thereby a comprehensive status about the requirements and the implementation of UNDERPIN, and it will be complemented with D1.3 and D3.2 by the end of the project, that will offer the final full picture of the deployed UNDERPIN Data Space.

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6 Annexes

Annex A - Use case templates

Table 14: UC1.1 overview

Title	Monitoring and predictive maintenance in the refinery
Description	A predictive maintenance algorithm will be developed that will allow for predicting equipment failure as well as detecting abnormal behaviour trends
Use case owner	MOH (maintenance)
Involved partners	MOH, AIT, SPH, INNOV
Assets	5 compressor machine groups from the main process of the refinery
Expected outcomes	Asset owner will be able to appropriately schedule maintenance works for impending failure, as well as apply corrective actions without interrupting operations based on detected abnormal behaviour
Datasets involved	Sensor data (temperature, pressure, vibration and axial displacement)
Data structures	Format: .xls/.csv Granularity: 5 minutes
Existing infrastructure	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Operations monitored through SAP and SCADA systems - Preexisting predictive maintenance model
Challenges	Insufficient failure data may lead to low accuracy of predictive algorithm

Table 15: UC2.1 overview

Title	Predictive maintenance in wind farms
Description	A predictive maintenance algorithm will be developed that will allow for predicting equipment failure as well as detecting abnormal behaviour trends
Use case owner	MORE (operations)
Involved partners	MORE, AIT, INNOV
Assets	Wind turbine generators from MORE's wind farm portfolio
Expected outcomes	Asset owner will be able to optimize operations based on detected abnormalities, as well as benchmark the maintenance works carried out by contractor
Datasets involved	Sensor data from multiple components within the wind turbine Fault alarms and warnings
Data structures	Format: .xls/.csv Granularity: Every 10 mins
Existing infrastructure	Operations monitored through proprietary SCADA systems offered by wind turbine manufacturers
Challenges	Loss of communication with wind turbines means alarms and errors may not always be detected

Table 16: UC2.2 overview

Title	Wind turbine blade repair prediction
Description	Statistical analysis of wind turbine blade damages from lightning strikes and prediction of necessary blade repairs based on relevant historical data
Use case owner	MORE (operations)
Involved partners	MORE, AIT
Assets	Wind farms from MORE's portfolio with focus on two wind farms equipped with lightning strike monitoring equipment
Expected outcomes	Asset owner will: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - gain deeper understanding on the impact of lightning strikes on wind turbine blades - be able to prevent impending blade failures by carrying out blade repairs in a timely manner
Datasets involved	Sensor data from multiple components within the wind turbine Fault alarms and warnings Historical data for peak current, time of lightning strike, strike intensity Blade repair historical data
Data structures	Format: .xls/.csv/.txt Granularity: Every 10mins
Existing infrastructure	Data collected through proprietary SCADA systems offered by wind turbine manufacturers Additional specialized data collected through Lightning Key Data (LKD) systems currently installed in two wind farms
Challenges	Low availability of lightning data since only two wind farms have LKD systems installed